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Smartphones: a new approach to the parallel-axis theorem

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ABSTRACT

The use of new technologies is a useful tool to approach the students to fundamental Physics problems. In particular, smartphones are the most common devices among the young people and may be suitable in multitude of basic Physics experiments.

Here, we report the use of the accelerometer sensor of a smartphone to visualize and demonstrate the parallel-axis theorem in a torsion pendulum. The study of the moment of inertia using a torsion pendulum is a typical example in the first courses of fundamentals of Physics. Several works have exposed different simple approaches to this system in order to make it attractive to the students. On the other hand, a recent trend to use the Smartphone's sensors has arisen in basic Physics lab practices, so the students work with instruments that are familiar to them. We attached a smartphone to a torsion pendulum in order to collect the acceleration time series and thus, i) to determine the stiffness of the spring, ii) to demonstrate the parallel-axis theorem and iii) to describe the Harmonic oscillations produced.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The use of new technologies to approach the students to fundamental Physics problems has stimulated several works along the last years. In particular, smartphones are the most common device among the young people. Here, we report the use of the accelerometer sensor of a smartphone to visualize and demonstrate the parallel-axis theorem [1] in a torsion pendulum.

The study of the inertia momentum by the use of the torsion pendulum is a typical example in the first courses of fundamentals of Physics. This example allows to explore the inertia momentum theory, the 2nd Newton's law, the Harmonic motion and the parallel-axis theorem all-in-one. Several works have exposed different simple approaches to this system [2-4] in order to make it attractive to the students. On the other hand, new learning strategies try to exploit the use of common devices in Physics lab practices. This way, the students work with familiar instruments to them. Thus, a recent trend to use the Smartphone's sensors has arisen, exploiting the possibilities of its accelerometer [5-6], ambient light [7] or microphone [8] sensors to describe Physics phenomena. Our experience by using the students' smartphones in class has always enthusiastically well perceived by them who have eagerly taken an active role.

Here, we present a study of the motion of a torsion pendulum coupled to a Smartphone in order to collect the dependence of the acceleration with respect of the time and thus, i) determine the stiffness of the spring, ii) demonstrate the parallel-axis theorem and iii) describe the Harmonic oscillations produced in this system.

2 THE TORSION PENDULUM

2.1 Theory

The torsion pendulum is an invaluable example of several fundamentals Physics laws. A torsion pendulum is composed with a rod, which rotates around its centre subjected to the force of a spring (stiffness k) and two known masses (m_1 , m_2) that may be placed at several distances from the centre of rotation.

Applying the Newton's second law to this system, we know that the force momentum or torque is related to the angular acceleration (α) and the inertia momentum (I). Therefore, the movement is dominated by the stiffness of the spring and the angle shifted (θ) with the following relation:

$$M_T = I\alpha = -k\theta \quad (1).$$

As the angular acceleration (α) derives from the rotated angle (θ), the equation that must be solved is:

$$\ddot{\theta} + \frac{k}{I}\theta = 0 \quad (2).$$

In a simple harmonic motion, the angular frequency (Ω) is related to the period (T), thus the solution of the previous equation is:

$$\Omega = \sqrt{\frac{k}{I}} = \frac{2\pi}{T} \quad (3).$$

The inertia momentum (I) of the system is the addition of the components and it can be calculated as:

$$I = I_{rod} + I_{m_1} + I_{m_2} \quad (4).$$

The parallel-axis (or Huygens-Steiner) theorem says that the inertia momentum around any axis (I_{m_2}), can be obtained from the inertia momentum, of a parallel-axis passing through the mass centre of the object (I_{m_0}), and the distance (d) between the two axis:

$$I_{m_2} = I_{m_0} + m_2 d^2 \quad (5).$$

This way, equation 4 can be rewritten as:

$$I = I_{rod} + I_{m_1} + I_{m_0} + m_2 d^2 = I_0 + m_2 d^2 \quad (6).$$

Where (I_0) is the inertia momentum of the system, around the rotation axis, except the corresponding to the mass m_2 . From *Eq. (3)* and *Eq. (6)*, the period squared of the oscillation is:

$$T^2 = \frac{4\pi^2 I}{k} = \frac{4\pi^2 I_0}{k} + \frac{4\pi^2 m_2}{k} d^2 \quad (7).$$

Thus *Eq. (7)* indicates that there is a linear relationship between the period squared of the oscillation and the distance of the mass to the rotation axis.

2.2 Experimental setup

In the experimental setup we replace the mass m_1 , of a torsion pendulum, with a smartphone, located at one end of the rod (*Fig. 1*). We use the accelerometer sensor in order to measure the accelerations, caused in the extreme of the rod, while a known-mass (m_2) is placed at several distances from the centre rotation. By means of a slight shift of the rod in the spring, the system starts to oscillate.

Fig. 1. Experimental setup developed to demonstrate the parallel axis theorem with a torsion pendulum coupled to a Smartphone.

Fig. 2. a) Smartphone in the extreme of the rod plotting the accelerations normal (a_x) and tangential (a_y). b) Snapshot of the application Physics Toolbox Suite [9]. The oscillation period (T) is overprinted.

The normal and tangential component, of the acceleration of the system (Fig. 2), are collected by the Android application Physics Toolbox Suite [8] taking advantage of the Smartphone's accelerometer sensor. The snapshot in Fig. 2 shows the oscillations and the period (T) is overprinted. Students see the harmonic nature of oscillations directly on the screen of their smartphones.

2.3 Results

The data gathered with the smartphone is exported to an Excel by means of csv files. For each position, d , of the mass m_2 of 0.236 kg, we calculate the period (T) of each oscillation and the average period ($T_{average}$). In our experiment we studied the oscillations of the tangential component of the acceleration. The experimental values, T^2 versus d^2 , are displayed in Fig. 3. A linear trend can be observed, according to the tendency expected by Eq. (7).

Thus, from the fit to a linear dependence through minimum squares and comparing with Eq. (7), we can obtain that the slope (a) is related to the stiffness of the spring as follows:

$$a = \frac{4\pi^2 m_2}{k} \quad (8).$$

And we calculate:

$$k_{measured} = \frac{4\pi^2 m_2}{a} \quad (9).$$

Fig. 3. Representation of the evolution T^2 vs d^2 . Linear fit is shown as dashed line.

Applying the Eq. (1), the value of the stiffness of the spring can be obtained:

$$k_{calculated} = \frac{|M_T|}{\theta} = \frac{F d_F}{\theta} \tag{10}$$

by the application of a force (F) at a determined distance (d_F) the rod rotates the angle (θ). We applied 0.25 N at a distance of 0.3 m and we observed that the rod rotated π radians.

In Table 1 we gather the essay parameters and the results calculated. The quality of the fit ($r^2 = 0.9999$) offered a large reliability of the parameters obtained. Also noteworthy is the fact, that the discrepancy in the calculation of the stiffness of the spring, by these both methods of is less than 4%.

Table 1. Essay parameters and results.

	Parameter	Value
	m_2 (kg)	0.236
Linear fit: $T^2 = a d^2 + b$	a (s^2/m^2)	402.9
	b (s^2)	27.79
	r^2	0.9999
	$k_{calculated}$ (Nm)	0.0240
	$k_{measured}$ (Nm)	0.0231

3 SUMMARY

In summary, we present a new way to calculate the stiffness of a spring applying previously acquired knowledge about inertia momentum and parallel-axis theorem thanks to the use of the accelerometer sensor of a Smartphone. This new method has been proved as an invaluable tool to make the experiments closer to the students and discover the potential possibilities of this common device as sensor in multitude of basic Physics experiments. In addition to the attractiveness for the students of using in a lab session a device of their own that they use constantly it is the fact that helps sorting out a problem we have with big groups at lab sessions as it may be the experimental costs. In this case it is extremely economical as smartphones are provided by the very students.

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